

Classification of Auditory Brainstem Responses through Symbolic Pattern Discovery

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Numeric time series are present in a very wide range of domains, including many branches of medicine. Data mining techniques have proved to be useful for knowledge discovery in this type of data and for supporting decision-making processes.

OBJECTIVES: The overall objective is to classify time series based on the discovery of frequent patterns. These patterns will be discovered in the symbolic sequences obtained from the time series data by means of a temporal abstraction process.

METHODS: We first transform numeric time series into symbolic time sequences where the symbols aim to represent the relevant domain concepts. These symbols can be defined using either public or expert domain knowledge. Then we apply a symbolic pattern discovery technique to the output symbolic sequences. This technique identifies the subsequences frequently found in a population group. These subsequences (patterns) are representative of population groups. Finally, we apply a classification technique based on the patterns found in order to classify new individuals. Thanks to the inclusion of domain knowledge, the classification results can be explained using the domain terminology, which makes the results easier to interpret for the domain specialist (physician).

RESULTS: This method has been applied to brainstem auditory evoked potentials (BAEP) time series. An experimentation plan has been implemented to analyse several aspects of the method including the best configuration of the pattern discovery technique parameters. After this we applied the method to the BAEPs of 83 individuals belonging to four classes (healthy, conductive hearing loss, vestibular schwannoma - brainstem involvement and vestibular schwannoma - 8th-nerve involvement). The results of the cross validation gave an overall accuracy of 99.4%, a sensitivity (recall) of 97.6% and a specificity of 100% (no false positives).

CONCLUSION: The proposed method performs an effective dimensionality reduction, and, if the symbolic transformation includes the proper domain knowledge, the method arguably outputs a data representation that denotes the relevant domain concepts more explicitly. The method is capable of finding patterns in BAEP time series and is very accurate at correctly predicting whether or not new patients have an auditory-related disorder.

Index Terms—Auditory Evoked Potentials, Data Mining, Decision Support Systems, Pattern-Based Classification, Symbolic Pattern Discovery, Time Series.

1. Introduction

Time series are a complex data type consisting of a potentially large sequence of values ordered in time. Time series appear in a wide range of domains such as medicine, astronomy, seismography, economy, climatology, etc. Over the last few years, the community of data mining scientists has taken an interest in research on time series, and countless medical applications have

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been **built** [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [A1]. Complex tests like electrocardiograms, electroencephalograms, evoked potentials, isokinetics tests, otoacoustic emissions, etc., are regularly performed in many fields of the medicine. The data recorded from these tests are time series that provide specialist physicians with very useful information for patient diagnosis. Physicians use their expert knowledge to analyse these time series looking for the signs characteristic of a disease or of a healthy person. In many cases, time series analysis is very complex, and physicians may find data mining techniques to be very helpful as they automate the process for identifying those signs [6].

There are many data mining techniques that analyse time series numerically. However, physicians in many medical domains are more interested in the morphology of the time series than in their numerical values. Experts often look for peaks, troughs, sudden ascents, peak sequences or other types of shapes, that is, anything that represents the time series behaviour. We present a technique capable of analysing a numeric time series which it transforms into a sequence of symbols that represent the time series behaviour. This symbolization process is capable of representing the time series in terms of the expert and the domain and also significantly reduces time series dimensionality.

Using this symbolic representation, we propose a method for classifying time series. This method searches for frequent subsequences (patterns) in the symbol sequences that could, under certain conditions, be a key diagnostic aid for physicians. This method, called SPC (symbolic pattern-based classification), is divided into the following steps:

1. Transform the numeric time series into symbolic time sequences that reflect relevant domain concepts
2. Mine sets of symbolic time sequences belonging to the same population group (class) to find their representative patterns.
3. Classify new symbolic time sequences based on the class patterns.

In order to evaluate our method, we applied it to the domain of brainstem auditory evoked potentials (BAEP) to detect conductive hearing loss and vestibular schwannoma abnormalities in a group of young people suspected of having hearing disorders. This study was performed in partnership with the Homero Castanier Crespo Hospital, Ecuador.

Auditory evoked potentials are the neuroelectric response of the auditory system to acoustic stimuli. They have been extensively used as a non-invasive electrophysiological tool for studying the human auditory system [7]. The measured signals are the result of many ionic currents associated with transduction processes that take place in the cochlear hair cells and with the generation of action potentials in the auditory nerve fibres. Depending on the time elapsed after stimulus onset, the evoked potentials can be classified as short-, medium- and long-latency potentials. The most commonly used potentials in clinical medicine are the short-latency BAEP which are measured during the first 10-15 milliseconds after stimulus onset. A common use of BAEP for clinical purposes is to diagnose hearing problems and brainstem tumours. The recorded data are time series with a duration of up to 15 ms that plots the evolution of the brainstem response to an acoustic stimulus against time.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we present a brief summary of key related work. In Section 3 we describe the proposed method and detail the symbolic transformation, pattern discovery and classification techniques. In Section 4 we present the BAEP domain on which the method has been applied and tested by means of several experiments. In Section 5 we report and briefly discuss the results. Finally, Section 6 outlines the conclusions.

2. Related Work

Two major groups of techniques for processing time series are numerical approaches and techniques based on time series morphology.

The most commonly used numerical techniques for time series analysis are the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) [8] and discrete wavelet transform (DWT) [9]. They represent the time series using a small number of coefficients, thereby reducing its dimensionality. The first k coefficients of the time series are used for comparison. The more alike the coefficients are, the more similar the respective time series are.

Other group of techniques focus on the morphology (the shape) of the time series rather than on the numeric values. The goal when comparing time series is to find series whose plots look similar even if they are on different scales. For example, two time series that peak at a similar timestamp might be similar even if they do not have the same values at that timestamp. According to this approach, time series that have a similar behaviour are regarded as being similar. These behaviours can be represented by symbols. This simplifies the complexity of the time series which is transformed into a symbolic time sequence

that aims to represent the relevant information that the original time series contains.

Selecting the most appropriate type of technique greatly depends on the domain and the set goals. On one hand, numerical techniques provide very accurate results but domain experts find them hard to understand. On the other hand, relevant domain concepts can be adopted in the data mining process using symbolic sequences. This is very important because the results can then be explained using the domain terminology [10]. An understandable explanation is a key issue on which user acceptance of a computer system hinges [11]. This is especially relevant in a medical domain and it is the main reason that led us to choose a symbolic approximation.

2.1 Symbolic representation of time series

A very important task in knowledge discovery processes from time series is to reduce the data dimensionality whereas retaining their key characteristics. Symbolic transformation is one of the most promising alternatives since it can represent the data in terms of the domain. It also has the advantage of implicitly removing noise through complexity reduction [12].

The idea of transforming a time series into a sequence of symbols (with a previously defined alphabet) that represents the original series with an acceptable loss of information is not new. Agrawal [13] proposed a shape definition language (SDL) with symbols like up, down, stable, etc. André-Jönsson [14] applied a similar idea to index time series. Discrete representations of time series have been output through segmentation. Some such proposals are based on piecewise approximation, like piecewise linear approximation (PLA) [15], [16], piecewise aggregate approximation (PAA) [17], adaptive piecewise constant approximation (APCA) [18] or multiresolution piecewise aggregate approximation (MPAA) [19]. Symbolic aggregate approximation (SAX) [20] performs a two-step time series transformation: first it discretizes the time series using PAA and then it symbolizes this representation into a symbolic string. Cassisi [21] proposes a transformation of time series into symbolic sequences that retains the most important original characteristics, e.g. local max and min, peaks, valleys, etc.

2.2 Pattern discovery

Frequent pattern discovery was first proposed by Agrawal [22] for discovering association rules in shopping cart transactions. A frequent pattern is a set of items that appear in a dataset with a frequency greater or equal to a predefined threshold. Many papers about this topic have been published in the wake of this seminal work.

Agrawal [23] stated an important property: a set of items with length k is frequent if and only if all of its subsets are frequent too. This property is called Apriori. Applying this property to frequent pattern discovery in time series, it can be said that frequent patterns of length 1 can be used to find patterns of length 2 and so on until it is not possible to find longer patterns.

Han [24] presented a proposal for discovering partial periodic frequent patterns in time series. This proposal combines three elements: a data cube [25], a bitmap technique and the Apriori property. Rather than searching for patterns with perfect periodicity, it uses a minimum support value to provide some level of flexibility. Han [26] proposes the FP-growth (frequent pattern growth) algorithm that uses a tree structure named FP-tree to store the frequent patterns in an incremental way. Agrawal's and Han's techniques are based on a horizontal representation of data (object_id², {Items}). On the other hand, Eclat (equivalence class transformation) [27] uses a vertical format (Item, {object_ids}) during the first scan to find level 1 patterns and then determines the higher level patterns by intersecting {object_ids} using the Apriori property. Although inspired by Han's proposal, our approach has some major differences, as discussed in Section 3.2.

Caraça-Valente [28] proposed an algorithm based on Apriori for discovering patterns in a set of numeric time series that takes into account also similar subseries. Chen [29] proposed an algorithm to find the time-interval sequential patterns, where the identified patterns are associated with the time interval in which the items happened. These two works deal with pattern discovery in numerical data.

Chen [30] proposed an algorithm to discover patterns in a set of categorical data streams. The time series are divided into windows with a predefined length to discover patterns that are repeated in n windows with $n > \text{minSup}$ (minimum support). Temporal interval tree association rules (TITAR) [31] is a model to extract association rules from big datasets expressed as symbolic sequences. Such techniques deal with symbolic sequences but do not share the goal of our work since they search for periodic patterns and association rules, respectively. An overview on frequent pattern mining can be found in [32].

² Object_id represents a transaction in Agrawal's work (Tid) and a time series in Han's research.

2.3 Pattern-based classification

Pattern-based classification is applied in many domains, such as industrial applications (character recognition, process control, signature analysis and speech analysis), medical applications (electroencephalogram analysis, genetic studies), government applications (smog detection and measurement, traffic analysis and control, fingerprint matching), military applications (sonar detection and classification, automatic target recognition), etc.

According to Olszewsky [33], time series classification comprises two stages: recognition of structural patterns and classification using structural patterns. Geurts [34] presented a pattern extraction technique for time series classification where series are represented using the PCA model, patterns identifying classes are defined using the points of discontinuity, and the signals are classified based on the defined patterns, using the 1-nearest neighbour algorithm. Zhang [35] presented a time series classification algorithm, which adopts a triangle distance function as a similarity measure, extracts patterns, and uses a traditional machine learning algorithm to create a classifier based on the extracted patterns. Li [36] presented the MNOE (mining non-overlap episode) algorithm to find non-overlapping frequent patterns in time series. Based on the information gain, significant frequent patterns are selected as the features for time series classification. Ye and Keogh [37] presented a time series shapelet discovery algorithm that finds subsequences from a set of time series to be used as primitives for time series classification. Batal [38] presented a framework for classifying medical multivariate time series. Time series are first discretized and converted into time-interval sequences using symbols (low, normal, high, very high) that represent percentile values and then a recent temporal pattern discovery process is performed and the resulting patterns are used to learn a time series classification model. Other approaches as [39] add a trend abstraction (increment, stable, decrement) to the transformation process.

3. Method

The aim of the proposed SPC (symbolic pattern-based classification) method is to classify the individuals (time series) of a population based on patterns that are representative of individuals that are members of the population group. We get the representative patterns from a set of training cases belonging to a class (population group, specific diagnosis, etc.). Then we use these patterns to classify new (unseen) cases. In our research, the term pattern refers to a sequence of symbols that appears in a relatively high percentage of symbolic time sequences from the same set (class). If we can assure that a pattern occurs in a high number of target group training cases and does not occur in the control group training cases, we could use the presence/absence of that pattern as an attribute for classifying target group individuals. The usefulness of this process in medicine is self-evident. If the target group is composed of patients with a known illness and the control group is composed of healthy patients, the pattern could be a useful symptom for diagnosing the illness.

The method has been built around three processes: symbolic transformation, pattern discovery and classification. The key point of our method is to use symbolic patterns to best represent the knowledge embedded in each time series in order to close the gap between human physicians and computer applications. This has been found to be useful [40] for explaining the results to the physicians in their own terms.

The outline of the SPC method is described as follows (each part of the method is detailed in Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3).

	FOR EACH CLASS, REPRESENTED BY A SET OF TRAINING CASES,
symbolic transformation process	<p>1. Transform each numeric time series into a symbolic time sequence in which the domain-specific concepts are embedded. This is a two-step procedure:</p> <p>1.1. Transform each numeric time series into a sequence of domain-independent symbols (e.g. peaks, ascents, etc.) based on the morphology of the time series.</p> <p>1.2. Characterize the domain-independent symbols output in 1.1 using expert knowledge. This includes removing irrelevant symbols and qualifying the other symbols according to their type. Type can represent the size, shape, relative position, etc., of the symbol in the time sequence. This step outputs the domain-dependent symbols sequence.</p>
pattern discovery process	<p>2. Find the frequent patterns in the set of symbolic time sequences: Search for the subsequences that appear in a high percentage of the symbolic sequences belonging to the same class.</p>
classification process	<p>3. Output the patterns that are exclusive to each class: Remove patterns also belonging to the control group (healthy patients) from the set of the class patterns.</p> <p>FOR EACH UNCLASSIFIED INDIVIDUAL,</p> <p>4. Classify the individual. To do this, take the following steps:</p> <p>4.1. Transform the individual time series into a symbolic time sequence as described in Step 1.</p> <p>4.2. Classify the symbolic time sequence. For each class, look for the presence of the class exclusive patterns in the symbolic sequence; if so, assign the corresponding individual to the class.</p>

Fig. 1 shows a graphical overview of the method.

Fig. 1. Symbolic pattern-based classification (SPC) method.

3.1 Symbolic Transformation

Domain experts acquire a great deal of expertise as they solve increasingly complex problems. In many cases, this expertise is outside the public domain. The inclusion of this knowledge in data mining algorithms is a complex task [33] primarily because data mining and domain experts speak different languages. They tend not to understand each other because they use a different terminology and way of reasoning.

In order to overcome these obstacles and use expert knowledge, numeric time series will be transformed into symbolic time sequences designed to explicitly represent the knowledge that the expert would have abstracted from the time series. This is a two-stage process, corresponding to Steps 1.1 and 1.2 of the proposed SPC method and is described in the next two sections.

3.1.1. Domain-independent symbolic transformation

The first stage of the transformation identifies the basic morphology (shape) of the time series, preserving the relevant information using domain-independent symbols (e.g. peaks, ascents, etc.) which are characterized by a number of properties whose values are extracted from the numeric time series. To do this, we use a domain-independent set of symbols, which correspond to generic forms. Fig. 2 shows a sample of the symbols used in the model, whereas Fig. 3 shows the data that have to be recorded to characterize a peak (initial, final and maximum values, amplitude and duration). These data may be different for each symbol.

Fig. 2. A sample of domain-independent (shape-based) symbols.

Fig. 3. Data required to characterize a peak.

During this stage, each numeric time series is transformed into a sequence of domain-independent symbols by parsing the time series (see Algorithm 1). This parsing detects in one pass which symbol corresponds to each segment of the time series.

The pointers mark landmarks for identifying the different symbols. For example, the cp pointer moves along the time series searching for changes of trend. It can detect three different statuses: ascent, descent and constant. A change in the status (change of trend) indicates the presence of a peak, a valley or a change from constant to ascent or descent, or vice versa. When a symbol has been detected, the data required to characterize that symbol is calculated and all the information is recorded.

```

Initialize (cp)                                     // cp points to first point of TS
While (not end of(TS))
  lp=cp
  status=Advance(cp)                                // moves one point to determine the 'status' (ascending,
                                                    // descending, constant)
  cp = NextChangeOfDirection(cp);                  // cp moves to the next change of direction
  Case status = 'Descending'
    FindDescendingSymbols(cp, lp, mp);              // searches for (Descent || Valley || Descent + Valley)
  Case status = 'Ascending'
    FindAscendingSymbols(cp, lp, mp);              // searches for (Ascent || Peak || Ascent + Peak)
  Case status = 'Constant'
    FindConstantSymbols(cp, lp);                   // searches for (Constant)
    Add Found Symbols to SymbolList                // with current values of cp, mp and lp
End While

```

Algorithm 1. Procedure for transforming a time series into a domain-independent symbol sequence.

3.1.2. Domain-dependent symbolic transformation

As stated in Step 1.2 of the proposed SPC method, the sequence of domain-independent symbols that has been extracted from the time series will be processed to output the domain-dependent symbols and their types. The domain-dependent symbols aim to represent the domain-specific concepts embedded in the time series. These symbols will also be qualified to identify important domain characteristics, like size, shape, relative location, etc. of the symbol in the time series. These domain-dependent symbols will be useful for decision making and also for explaining the results in the domain terminology.

Experts will be readily able to understand explanations of the reasoning process and results that use concepts that are familiar to the expert and the domain. This is especially important in domains like medicine, where diagnosis is exclusively the responsibility of the physician and the diagnosis has to be duly explained. The gap between the conceptual model and the domain has to be reduced, resulting in a more direct and easier interaction with domain experts. This will help to solve in part the problems mentioned in [41], [33] concerning the inclusion of expertise in data mining methods.

The process enacted in Step 1.2 of the SPC method is detailed in Algorithm 2. This process uses a set of heuristic rules to determine how to transform each domain-independent symbol into a domain-dependent symbol. Note that this can be a one-to-one transformation or a many-to-one in which several domain-independent symbols results in a single domain-dependent symbol. A simplified example of heuristic is shown at the bottom of Algorithm 2³.

³ All the examples related to the electrocardiography domain are used only for illustration purposes and do not intend to provide accurate information.

Input: a domain-independent symbols Time Sequence T_{in}
Output: the corresponding domain-dependent (typed) symbols Time Sequence T_{out}

```

For i=1 to Length( $T_{in}$ )
  H = FindHeuristics( $T_{in}[i]$ )           // Checks heuristics for symbol  $T_{in}[i]$ 
  h = SelectHeuristic(H,  $T_{in}[i]$ )       // Selects the most appropriate heuristic for the
                                         // subsequence  $T_{in}[i].. T_{in}[i+n]$  where n depends on
                                         // the heuristic
  ds = ApplyHeuristic(h,  $T_{in}[i]$ )       // Returns the obtained domain-dependent symbol ds
                                         // and n
  If ds  $\neq$  null
    Then
      typed_ds = SpecifyType(ds),         // Based on the Symbolic Limits Table
      Add typed_ds to  $T_{out}$ ;             // Incrementally builds the domain-dependent time
                                         // sequence
      i = i + n;                          // n is the # of domain-independent symbols used to
                                         // match the ds symbol
    Else i = i + 1                       // Removes the irrelevant domain-independent symbols
  End For
// Example of heuristic in the electrocardiography domain
If  $T_{in}[i]$  = Valley AND  $T_{in}[i+1]$  = Peak AND  $T_{in}[i+2]$  = Valley
  Then If  $0,6sec \leq T_{in}[i+2].vf - T_{in}[i].vi \leq 0,12sec$  AND  $T_{in}[i].duration < 0,4 * T_{in}[i+1].duration$ 
  AND ...
    Then ds.symbol = QRScomplex
          ds.duration =  $T_{in}[i+2].vf - T_{in}[i].vi$ 
          ds.amplitude = ...
          n=3
  ...

```

Algorithm 2. Domain-dependent symbolic transformation.

Fig. 4 shows the mapping between the time series, the domain-independent sequence and the domain-dependent sequence. Focusing on the domain-dependent symbols, Fig. 4 shows how some of them correspond to a single domain-independent symbol (e.g., Peak to P wave), some others correspond to several domain-independent symbols (e.g., Valley-Peak-Valley to QRS complex) and in some cases the domain-independent symbol are directly disregarded (e.g. the last valley). It is worth noting that our symbols do not correspond to relevant events that take place in the time series. Rather than this the whole time series is transformed into a sequence of symbols that aims to be equivalent to the original time series.

Fig. 4. Electrocardiogram time sequence with the corresponding domain-independent and domain-dependent sequences.

The domain-dependent symbols have to be qualified. The SpecifyType() function (see Algorithm 2) takes a domain-dependent symbol and outputs the respective typed symbol. It uses the information stored in the Symbolic Limits table. This

table stores the conditions that the data that characterize each symbol must meet in order to be assigned a particular type.

For example, applied to electrocardiography (Fig. 5), the domain-independent symbolic transformation step would output the valley-peak-valley sequence. The domain-dependent symbolic transformation would, under certain conditions, convert this sequence into a symbol called QRS complex. There are many types of QRS complex. Therefore this symbol needs to be qualified to define its type. For example, a normal QRS complex (QRS.normal) must have a duration of between 60 and 100 milliseconds and a voltage of less than or equal to 3.5 mV). A QRS.wide (duration greater than 100 milliseconds) could be used for diagnosis support as symptomatic of tachycardia.

Fig. 5. Electrocardiogram snippet with QRS complex [42].

Finally, the domain-dependent symbol list, i.e. the symbolic time sequence, is stored in a relational table named *SymbolicTimeSequences*. For simplicity's sake, we have represented each typed symbol as a char (an uppercase or lowercase letter). For instance, the typed symbol QRS.normal in Fig. 5 could be the character "C", and the QRS.wide could be represented by the character "D". This set of characters constitutes the alphabet of domain-dependent symbols.

The domain knowledge required to perform the domain-dependent symbolic transformation must be acquired through knowledge acquisition techniques. We will describe in section 4.1. the knowledge acquisition process carried out on the BAEP domain.

3.2 Pattern discovery

The main goal of our method is to find patterns that are representative of the different classes of domain individuals. Patterns are subsequences of time series that are repeated with some frequency in a given set of time series. If these sets are representative of relevant population groups, the repeated presence of such patterns could characterize the respective groups, and the patterns could, therefore, be used in classification processes to identify new group members.

The proposed pattern discovery technique should scan all the symbolic time sequences of a particular group of people and find repeated subsequences, taking into account that the same subsequence may appear at different positions of the symbolic time sequences.

Obviously, it is not feasible for a subsequence with exactly the same values to be repeated in numeric time series. Issues such as the inherent error of the measurement sensors, noise or even small changes in values can produce small differences in the series. However, these differences may not be significant from the point of view of the domain, in which case the respective subsequences should be considered equal. This problem will be partially solved once the numeric time series have been transformed into symbolic sequences. However, we believe that it is still useful to consider some margin of dissimilarity. On one hand, these small numerical changes in values close to the points that determine one symbol or another could lead to different symbolic sequences and, on the other hand, it also makes sense not to require an absolute match for long patterns

composed of many symbols. To measure the distance between symbolic sequences we have used the Manhattan distance⁴ (or L1-norm) and a cost matrix to specify the distance between each pair of typed symbols.

The pattern discovery is the core phase of the method as it is where knowledge will be extracted from the sets of time series. We will define a pattern as a symbolic subsequence that frequently appears in a set of time sequences in any position within the sequences. The term “frequently” will be given by a support threshold called *minsupport* that denotes the percentage of time sequences within the set in which the patterns appear at least once. Also, in order to take into account similar subsequences we will use the *maxdist* parameter to define the maximum distance between two subsequences for them to be considered the same.

To find the patterns that appear in a given set of time sequences, we will use an incremental algorithm. This algorithm was inspired by state-of-the-art ideas and the Apriori property but required major adaptations to fit our particular objectives, mainly due to the following:

- the need to find similar and not just identical subsequences, and
- the fact that patterns have to be found across a set of time sequences (not just in one time sequence) and that they can appear at any position in the time series.

To represent the symbolic time sequence data, the algorithm uses a data cube (a three-dimensional array of bits) inspired by Han’s working cube [24] but adapted to the needs of our symbolic pattern discovery problem (see Fig. 6). The main differences are:

- the dimensions of our cube are symbol position, time sequence and symbols instead of time index, index period and value of the series, respectively. This change results in major differences in the information management processes.
- Han uses the cube to get the patterns that appear in the different periods of a single time series. However, our method outputs the patterns present in a set of time series. One option would be to address our problem in the same manner as Han, considering our different time series as the different periods of Han’s single series. But, even using this analogy, there is an important difference because the patterns may, in our case, be located at different positions within their respective time series, whereas Han’s periodic patterns must appear at the same relative position in each period.

Fig. 6. Proposed adaptations to Han’s Working Cube.

The pattern discovery technique searches for the patterns of length 1. Once it has found these patterns, it searches for patterns of length 2, which are then used as a basis for searching for patterns of length 3 and so on until no new patterns are found. In our research, a pattern of length k is called a kpattern. Our pattern discovery technique uses the Apriori property, which means that if a subsequence is not a pattern, none of its supersets (subsequences containing it) can be a pattern. In this case, the respective branch of the search tree can be pruned. Based on the Apriori property, the list of candidate 2patterns is built combining two 1patterns. The algorithm then checks which of these candidates are frequent enough to be considered 2patterns. The list of candidate 3patterns is built by combining each of the 2patterns with each of the 1patterns, and so on.

⁴ Once the similarity between the numeric series is partially assumed by the transformation into symbolic sequences, this distance is sufficient. We did not consider it necessary to use edit distances, which would require major changes to the frequent pattern search process.

The *minsupport* threshold used to determine whether a subsequence is frequent can be used to improve algorithm efficiency. As its *minsupport* value is usually close to 1, we can use the one's complement of its value ($1 - \text{minsupport}$) to discard the subsequences that cannot be patterns. Thus, when *minsupport* is greater than 0.5, we count the number of sequences that do not have the pattern and when it is greater than $1 - \text{minsupport}$, the branch is discarded (and we stop searching for any more occurrences of this subsequence).

We use a data structure called *kPatternIndexer* to easily access the positions in the time sequences at which patterns of length k (i.e. *k*patterns) occur. *kPatternIndexer* consists of a two-dimensional array of integer lists, where each list stores the positions in a time sequence TS_i containing each pattern of length k . This information is used to find the patterns of length $k+1$. Fig. 7 shows an example of a *k*pattern indexer structure for $k=1$ (that is, subsequences composed of one single symbol S_i) and a slice corresponding to a time sequence with the positions of its 1patterns.

Fig. 7. The *k*pattern indexer for $k=1$.

The proposed pattern discovery method is described in Algorithm 3.

Input: Set of symbolic time sequences for a population group; alphabet of domain-dependent symbols⁵; *minsupport* ; *maxdist*.

Output: The set of patterns *patternList*.

Create the Data Cube. /* If the symbol s_m appears at i -th position of the time sequence TS_j , the respective cell (i,j,m) is filled with 1, else its value is 0 */

1. $patternList = \emptyset$

2. Pattern discovery initialization step: // Build the length=1 pattern list and 1PatternIndexer
 $k=1$

For each time sequence

For each symbol s in the time sequence

Save its position in the 1PatternIndexer

If any symbol s is not present in at least $(1 - \text{min-conf}) * n$ sequences /* n is the total number of time sequences */

Then prune symbol s /* s will not be considered a 1pattern and is removed from the 1PatternIndexer */

Else $patternList = patternList \cup \{s\}$ // add the 1pattern s to patternList

End For

End For

Pattern discovery inductive iteration: /* With the data structures output at iteration $k-1$, find the *k*patterns and build the *k*PatternIndexer */

Repeat

$k=k+1$ //in the first iteration k will be 2

⁵ Note that these symbols are the typed symbols obtained in the domain dependent symbolic transformation (Step 1.2 of the SPC method) and are represented as chars

```

kPatternIndexer =  $\emptyset$ 
For each k-1pattern
  For each 1pattern
    kpc = k-1pattern  $\oplus$  1pattern // kpc is a candidate kpattern
    NotFound_kpc_Count = 0;
    For each time sequence  $TS_j$ 
      For each position p of the k-1pattern registered in the k-1PatternIndexer
        If located (kpc, p) /* checks if symbols present from position p to p+k-1
          are below maxdist of kpc */
          Then
            include  $TS_j$  and p in tempIndex;
            found = true
        End For
      If not found // candidate kpc is not in time sequence  $TS_j$ 
        Then
          NotFound_kpc_Count ++
          If NotFound_kpc_Count > (1 - minsupport) * n
            Then Break // Prune: kpc cannot be frequent
    End For
  If NotFound_kpc_Count > (1 - minsupport) * n /* if candidate kpc is not frequent */
    Then Break
  Else
    patternList = patternList  $\cup$  {kpc}
    Add tempIndex to kPatternIndexer for kpc
  End For
End For
Until (kPatternIndexer is empty) // There are no patterns of length k so new pattern cannot be found

```

Fig. 8 illustrates how the pattern discovery algorithm works. The input is a set of symbolic time sequences belonging to the same population group. The objective is to find patterns that characterize the group. In this example we assume that there are seven symbols in the domain, and three of them (S_0 , S_2 and S_5) appear frequently in the time sequences. Therefore they are 1patterns and are added to the patternList. The candidate 2patterns are generated by combining each 1pattern with any other 1pattern. The frequent 2patterns on this list of candidate 2patterns (highlighted in Fig. 8) are added to the patternList. This procedure is repeated until no more kpatterns are found. In this example, this happens at level 4, where the kpatternIndexer is empty and no more changes will be made to the patternList. The pattern discovery process ends here, and the pattern list containing eight different patterns is output.

Fig. 8. Example of pattern discovery.

found for a particular illness (unhealthy patients) and the patterns for the control group (healthy patients). The output unhealthy class-exclusive patterns are used to classify a new patient (in Fig. 9, the new patient sequence has the patterns of unhealthy patients and is therefore labelled as Unhealthy).

Fig. 9. Patterns⁶ for classifying patients.

4. Case Study: Brainstem Auditory Evoked Potentials (BAEP)

To evaluate our method we have chosen the Brainstem Auditory Evoked Potentials (BAEP) domain. The main goal in this domain is to diagnose auditory problems and brainstem tumours through the analysis of patient responses to acoustic stimuli. These responses are electrophysiological potentials (BAEPs) recorded by high precision equipment that is connected to the patient by means of sensors attached to three points of the head. The BAEPs are registered by a computer that receives and stores the digitalized values (sampled every 16 microseconds) as a time series with a duration of from 0 to 15 milliseconds. Fig. 10 shows a layout of the devices for measuring BAEPs.

Typically, the acoustic stimulus that is sent to the patient’s auditory system is a click. The response is a set of potentials whose values are associated with time instants. As there are countless response signal contaminants during this process, the patient is actually stimulated with around 2000 clicks in order to calculate a mean signal whose noise is thus averaged so as not to be significant.

Fig. 10. Schema for the BAEP data gathering.

An important characteristic of a click is intensity. Normally, the specialized equipment can apply stimuli of up to 120 dB

⁶ In order to simplify the examples, only identical pattern matches are shown.

(decibels), but, in practice, BAEP tests are typically run at intensities of 70 dB, 50 dB and 30 dB.

Fig. 11 shows a typical BAEP time series elicited at 70 dB. As we found from the interviews with the expert, an BAEP has a number of relevant peaks, called waves, which are labelled with roman numerals. To identify these waves, it is important to know the instant when they occur (latency), and the time intervals between two waves, called interwave intervals, are also equally important for diagnosis. Consequently, we have decided to introduce three wave types (wave I, wave III, wave V) and the corresponding interwave intervals as new domain-dependent symbols. Fig. 11 shows the regions in the time series that correspond to these domain-dependent symbols.

Fig. 11. BAEP time series registered at intensity of 70 dB.

4.1 Domain knowledge formalization

The domain information is stored in a relational database whose conceptual model is shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. Relational database structure.

Initially, the database must be filled with the data related to the symbols, symbol types and costs (distances) between typed symbols that will be used to compute the distance between subsequences. This information is gathered, through a public knowledge and expert knowledge acquisition process. The output of this process is a set of domain-dependent symbols with their respective types.

In the BAEP case study the domain knowledge was gathered primarily through a series of interviews with the expert but also by analysing public knowledge. In the interviews the expert evaluated a set of BAEP time series to identify the relevant parts (corresponding to domain-dependent symbols: waves and interwaves in the BAEP domain) and assessed their characteristics. Then, a prototype was implemented and the resulting symbolic sequences were shown to the expert for evaluation. As a result of this evaluation, some changes were made to the prototype. This process ended when the prototype provided the correct symbols and symbol qualifications in a high percentage of the cases (over 98%). It took three to five iterations depending on how hard it was to interpret each symbol. In the later iterations the results were also shown to other

neurophysicians to assure a more generalized and less biased perspective. Table I shows the symbols and their types for the BAEP domain.

TABLE I
DOMAIN-DEPENDENT SYMBOLS AND THEIR TYPES FOR THE BAEP DOMAIN

DOMAIN-DEPENDENT SYMBOLS	SYMBOL TYPES
Wave I	Delayed Normal Advanced
Wave III	Delayed Normal Advanced
Wave V	Delayed Normal Advanced
Interwave interval I-III	Short Normal Long
Interwave interval III-V	Short Normal Long
Interwave interval I-V	Short Normal Long

4.2 Data selection

From the available historical data on auditory problems analysed using the BAEP technique, we selected three possible diagnoses (classes):

- vestibular schwannoma with brainstem involvement,
- vestibular schwannoma with 8th-nerve involvement, and
- conductive hearing loss.

Apart from the time series for each of the above diagnoses, we also collected a number of cases of healthy patients. After the data cleaning process, we had a total of 83 numeric time series, including some that were produced specifically for this study on the at-risk population. Considering that this is a very specialized domain, where tests are expensive and only data from tests performed using the same medical protocol under extremely similar conditions should be selected, the number of cases is acceptable.

Every time series was labelled with its respective class. All labelled data were loaded into the database as numeric time series (and converted into symbolic time sequences by the symbolic transformation module). Table II shows the data distribution by classes (every time series belongs to just one class).

TABLE II
CASES DIVIDED BY CLASSES

CLASS	# CASES
Healthy	41
Conductive hearing loss	23
Vestibular schwannoma - brainstem involvement	9
Vestibular schwannoma - 8th-nerve involvement	10
TOTAL	83

4.3 Experimentation plan

We drew up an experimentation plan with two objectives. First, we aimed to show that a temporal abstraction including domain-dependent knowledge can be more beneficial than the use of numerical methods in some domains. To do this, we ran

a simple experiment using the Fourier transform and the X-means clustering algorithms. Second, we meant to check that the pattern discovery technique finds relevant patterns for each class (suitable for classification purposes), as well as looking for the best configuration of the pattern discovery technique parameters in order to achieve the best possible results in the classification task.

4.3.1 On the usefulness of temporal abstraction methods

The most relevant concepts for diagnosis in the BAEP domain are the three above-mentioned waves and the intervals between them. Other waves or peaks that occur in the time series are not relevant for the decision-making process. On this ground, we suspect that numerical methods will not perform well when comparing or classifying the series. To check this point, we used the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to transform the time series into vectors of coefficients, compare them using the Euclidean distance and group them using a clustering method. This is the probably the most used procedure when time series are analysed by means of numeric techniques. We selected 43 time series divided into four balanced classes:

- Healthy (12 cases)
- Conductive hearing loss (12)
- Schwannoma brainstem involvement (9)
- Schwannoma 8th-nerve involvement (10).

The X-means clustering algorithm [43] was applied to the series transformed using the DFT, and the four output clusters are shown in Figure 13. Each individual in Figure 13 is coloured according to its known class, as stated in the legend.

Fig. 13. Distribution of the 43 clustered instances.

The resulting clusters and real classes to which the time series belong are very different as regards the uneven distribution of the clusters and the assignment of the individuals to the clusters. None of the clusters has a majority of individuals of one single class (with the trivial exception of cluster 3), and there is no class that is included in a single cluster. The reason for these very poor results are that the joint use of the DFT and the Euclidean distance focuses on the absolute value of the time series at each point and not on the overall shape of the series. Additionally, the algorithm considers not only the relevant waves but all possible waves in the series. Therefore, the relevant waves have less relative importance. Even though this is a simple experiment, the results are so poor as to rule out the use of this type of numerical methods.

4.3.2 Pattern discovery technique: testing and parameterization

To focus the analysis on the pattern discovery technique, we chose the simplest classification task, considering only one class (unhealthy patients) and the control group (healthy patients). Specifically, we used all the cases (a total of 83) for the experiment, of which 42 correspond to unhealthy and 41 to healthy individuals. Five different configurations of the pattern discovery technique were applied to these data by tuning the *minsupport* and *maxdist*. We chose the five configurations that the experience acquired during the preliminary tests suggested were the most promising. A five-fold cross validation process was carried out for each configuration.

The experiment was carried out according to the following procedure:

Repeat 5 times:

1. Select a parameter configuration (*minsupport*, *maxdist*)
2. Apply the pattern discovery technique to the selected classes: positive class “*Unhealthy*” and negative class “*Healthy*”
3. Classify data according to the exclusive patterns found using a five-fold cross validation process
4. Compute the performance measures that will be used to evaluate the results

Tables III summarizes the results of the cross validation process for each of the five selected configurations. It also shows the classifier performance for each configuration. We have used the appropriate performance measures for medical domains [11] and binary classification, described in Table IV. Looking at Table III, we find that classifier effectiveness increases at higher values of *minsupport* and at lower values of *maxdist*. Therefore, the best parameter configuration is *minsupport* = 0.95 and *maxdist* = 0. This indicates that the most reliable configuration searches for identical and not just similar patterns.

TABLE III
CLASSIFIER PERFORMANCE FOR THE FIVE CONFIGURATIONS

Parameter values	tp	fp	fn	tn	A	R	S	F ₁
<i>minsupport</i> = 0.90 <i>maxdist</i> = 0.20	32	12	10	29	0.735	0.762	0.707	0.744
<i>minsupport</i> = 0.90 <i>maxdist</i> = 0.00	37	6	5	35	0.867	0.881	0.854	0.870
<i>minsupport</i> = 0.95 <i>maxdist</i> = 0.10	34	11	8	30	0.771	0.810	0.732	0.782
<i>minsupport</i> = 0.95 <i>maxdist</i> = 0.05	38	6	4	35	0.880	0.905	0.854	0.884
<i>minsupport</i> = 0.95 <i>maxdist</i> = 0.00	42	2		39	0.976	1.000	0.951	0.977

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR BINARY CLASSIFICATION

Measure	Formula	Description
Accuracy (A)	$\frac{tp + tn}{tp + fp + tn + fn}$	Accuracy measures the overall effectiveness of the classifier.
Sensitivity or recall (R)	$\frac{tp}{tp + fn}$	Also called true positive rate (TPR), sensitivity measures how effective the classifier is at identifying the individuals of the positive class.
Specificity (S)	$\frac{tn}{tn + fp}$	Also called true negative rate (TNR), specificity measures how effective the classifier is at identifying the individuals of the negative class.
F ₁ score (F ₁)	$\frac{2 \times precision \times recall}{precision + recall}$	F ₁ score combines precision ($tp/tp+fp$) and recall. It is shown here for completeness but should be used with caution in medicine as it does not take into account the tn.

This experiment is also useful for drawing positive conclusions with respect to the effectiveness and robustness of the pattern discovery technique because the classification results using different parameter configurations are consistently well above 70% accuracy. As the classes are balanced in this experiment, accuracy is a good overall performance measure of the classifier.

The classifier has the option of establishing a new parameter that determines the percentage of class patterns that need to be found in one individual for the individual to be classified in that class. In the BAEP domain, each of the diagnoses used in our experiments are associated with a relatively high number of patterns. This raises the question of whether each and every class pattern necessarily has to be found in order to classify an individual. In response to this question, we added a new parameter called *ppc* (percentage of patterns for classification) to indicate the percentage of patterns that need to be found to classify an

individual.

In order to empirically find the most appropriate value for this parameter, we designed an experiment with all available data. Several execution runs were carried out varying this parameter within the range of 20% to 100% in order to ascertain the values that deliver the best classification results. As a result of the experiment, we found that there is a lower percentage bound for each class as of which the classification performance no longer improves. Below this lower bound, the number of false positive increases. Table V shows the optimal operating range for the *ppc* parameter by class. Looking at this table, we find that the classifier outputs the same overall results for *ppc* values between 70% and 100%. We opted for the most restrictive value in this range (*ppc*=100) as, generally, the number of false positives (fp) would tend to increase and the number of true negatives (tn) to decrease if we were to be less restrictive. In the latter case, the sensitivity rate would be unchanged, but the specificity rate would decrease which is not a desirable behaviour in medical domains.

TABLE V
PPC OPTIMAL RANGES FOR EACH CLASS

Class	Optimal range for <i>ppc</i>
Healthy	50 to 100%
Conductive Hearing Loss	40 to 100%
Schwannoma 8th-nerve	60 to 100%
Schwannoma Brainstem	70 to 100%

5. Results and Discussion

In this section we present the final results of applying the SPC method to the BAEP data once information acquired during the experimentation process was incorporated into the method. As stated in Table II, the available patient records are 83 time series belonging to four classes: 41 cases correspond to healthy patients that will be used as a control group, whereas the remaining 42 cases are distributed across the three above-mentioned illnesses. Due to the relatively small size of two of these classes, a three-fold cross validation was carried out for the classification process. The respective confusion matrices are shown in Tables VI.a to VI.c.

TABLE VI
THE CONFUSION MATRICES FOR THE THREE-FOLD CROSS VALIDATION

	Predicted Class					Total
	c1	c2	c3	c4	u	
c1	13	0	0	0	1	14
c2	0	7	0	0	0	7
c3	0	0	3	0	0	3
c4	0	0	0	4	0	4
Total	13	7	3	4	1	28

	Predicted Class					Total
	c1	c2	c3	c4	u	
c1	13	0	0	0	1	14
c2	0	8	0	0	0	8
c3	0	0	3	0	0	3
c4	0	0	0	3	0	3
Total	13	8	3	3	1	28

	Predicted Class					Total
	c1	c2	c3	c4	u	
c1	13	0	0	0	0	13
c2	0	8	0	0	0	8
c3	0	0	3	0	0	3
c4	0	0	0	3	0	3
Total	13	8	3	3	0	27

c1 Healthy
c2 Conductive Hearing Loss
c3 Vestibular Schwannoma 8th-nerve
c4 Vestibular Schwannoma Brainstem
u Unclassified

As this is a multiclass classification problem, we use the appropriate multiclass performance measures, described in Table VII, (adapted from [44]) to calculate the classifier performance. There are two types of measures: the micro-average (denoted by μ) that gives a weighted average taking into account the size of each class and the macro-average (denoted by M) that returns an average attaching the same weight to all the classes.

TABLE VII
PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR MULTICLASS CLASSIFICATION

Measure	Formula	Description
Average Accuracy (AA)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{tp_i + tn_i}{tp_i + fn_i + fp_i + tn_i}}{n}$	Average effectiveness by class.
Sensitivity _M or Recall _M (R _M)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{tp_i}{tp_i + fn_i}}{n}$	Average sensitivity of each class. It attaches equal weight to each class.
Sensitivity _μ or Recall _μ (R _μ)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n tp_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n tp_i + fn_i}$	Similar to Sensitivity _M but computing the average weight according to the size of each class, since it attaches equal weight to each individual classification.
Specificity _M (S _M)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{tn_i}{tn_i + fp_i}}{n}$	Average specificity of each class. It attaches equal weight to each class.
Specificity _μ (S _μ)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n tn_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n tn_i + fp_i}$	Similar to Specificity _M but computing the average weight according to the size of each class.

Table VIII summarizes the classifier performance for the three-fold cross validation classification process.

TABLE VIII
PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR THE THREE FOLDS AND THE SUMMARIZED VALUES FOR THE CLASSIFICATION METHOD

Run	Class	tp	fp	fn	tn	AA	S _μ	S _M	R _μ	R _M
1	c1	13	0	1	14	0.991	1.000	1.000	0.964	0.982
	c2	7	0	0	20					
	c3	3	0	0	24					
	c4	4	0	0	23					
2	c1	13	0	1	14	0.991	1.000	1.000	0.964	0.982
	c2	8	0	0	19					
	c3	3	0	0	24					
	c4	3	0	0	24					
3	c1	13	0	0	14	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	c2	8	0	0	19					
	c3	3	0	0	24					
	c4	3	0	0	24					
TOTAL	c1	39	0	2	42	0.994	1.000	1.000	0.976	0.988
	c2	23	0	0	58					
	c3	9	0	0	72					
	c4	10	0	0	71					

c1 Healthy
c2 Conductive Hearing Loss
c3 Vestibular Schwannoma – 8th-nerve
c4 Vestibular Schwannoma – Brainstem

The results shown in Table VIII are very promising. An overall sensitivity (recall) of 0.97 and a specificity of 1 (i.e., there are no false positives) are very good indicators in a medical domain. This is due, on one hand, to the good performance of the pattern discovery and classification techniques but also to the symbolic transformation process. The use of domain knowledge in this transformation is a crucial step for achieving these results.

6. Conclusions

We have developed a time series classification method based on symbolic pattern discovery, which we have applied to the BAEP domain. The results show that the method is capable of finding patterns in BAEP time series and is very accurate at correctly predicting whether or not new patients have an auditory-related disorder. These results suggest that the proposed data mining method is very suitable for this domain.

The method has a number of parameters (*minsupport*, *maxdist* and *ppc*) that can be adjusted to the optimum configuration for any particular domain. We have presented a simple procedure for calibrating these parameters in order to achieve the best possible results. Performance measures were taken for five parameter configurations (Table III). According to the results, classifier performance reaches its highest value when *minsupport* = 0.95 and *maxdist* = 0.0 (with *ppc*=1), that is, a very high minimum support and zero tolerance for the distance between symbolic subsequences.

The proposed method performs an effective dimensionality reduction, and, if the symbolic transformation includes the proper domain knowledge, the method arguably outputs a data representation that denotes the relevant domain concepts more explicitly.

The proposed method's need for expert or public knowledge can be viewed as a weakness. However, the only domain-dependent part of the method is the definition of symbols for the symbolic transformation step. This step can be performed with the help of a graphical interface, which the medical specialist that participated in this research found to be very manageable during the BAEP case study. As the results show, this domain-dependent knowledge greatly improves the effectiveness of the classifier and also makes this tool more acceptable for physicians as the results can be explained using the same concepts that the physician uses on a regular basis. In other words, the method does not behave like a black box producing a diagnosis that physician would find hard to accept, but instead provides an explanation of the output diagnosis in the physicians' own language. For example, "patient x may have a vestibular schwannoma disorder as waveIII is delayed and interwaveI-V is long".

The proposed method can be of great help to both expert and novice physicians reducing their workload by automatically computing the information about the input data that are relevant in the domain and also giving on decision-making process support related to diagnostic tasks in domains such as BAEP or any other domain with time series data.

Numerical methods are not appropriate in many domains where the relevant concepts are directly related to the time series morphology rather than to timestamp values. BAEP is an example of such a domain since the important concepts are whether particular peaks appear earlier or later, as well as the time elapsed between those peaks. This is just one example of how any domain idiosyncrasy can be captured by the proposed domain-dependent symbolic transformation technique. It is these particular domain characteristics that render domain-independent methods inefficient, as this information would be almost impossible to acquire using such domain-independent methods.

As a future line of research we are planning to introduce an edit distance to compute the distance between symbolic sequences. This could prove to be a better way for measuring similarity within this kind of data but has the downside that the Apriori property would no longer hold in every case. This would result in a less efficient pattern discovery algorithm.

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